

Information Theory and A Conserved Substance During Signal Interactions?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 6, 2020

One may obtain equilibrium particle number distributions in statistical mechanics by applying time reversal balance to reactions which conserve energy. For example, one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by using $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$, taking \ln of both sides and equating to: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. For more complicated situations, one may use “reaction probabilities” instead of particle number probabilities i.e. $g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_4))$. Taking \ln of both sides and equating to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ yields more complicated distributions such as the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein distribution for which $g=f/(1-f)$ and $g=f/(1+f)$. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one may define Shannon’s entropy density $-f \ln(f)$ which when varied with respect to f subject to the constraint $1/T \sum e_i f(e_i)$ yields the MB distribution. For the more complicated case, one may define a Shannon’s entropy density for $g(f(e_i))$ i.e. $-g \ln(g)$.

In information theory, matters seem to be different i.e. one does not seem to have energy conserving interactions. For instance, one may start with a long message written in English for which there is a probability P_i for each letter to occur. The message is then transmitted and it is possible that an “a” in the original message is converted to a different letter in the received message. It seems, however, that P_i must remain the same in the received message. If this were not the case, the transmission would immediately be suspect. Given this constraint, it seems one may consider each initial letter undergoing interactions until it arrives at the reception point. If P_i is unchanged, it seems there is a conserved quantity in the system and we try to show that it is $\ln(P_i)$ i.e. information.

The situation of P_i remaining unchanged during “interactions” also applies to statistical mechanical equilibrium because one begins with $f(e_i)$ in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, and even though each particle may change its energy through numerous interactions, after time t , $f(e_i)$ must be the same for there to be equilibrium. We argue that this is the link between information theory and statistical mechanics. As far as we know, this view is not included in descriptions of information theory which compare it to statistical mechanics.

Statistical Mechanics and Reaction Balance

Statistical mechanics is often presented in terms of microcanonical distributions (factorial counting of arrangements), canonical partition functions with weights $\exp(-E/T)$ and grand canonical partition functions with weights of $\exp(-1/T(E-uN))$. Thus, the idea of conservation of energy in reactions does not seem particularly important. If one considers reaction balance in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, however, energy conservation is key. One may describe two body scattering by:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ Taking } \ln \text{ and equating to } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \text{ yields } f(e_i)= C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

Thus, $\ln(f(e_i))$ is a conserved quantity in such a reaction, even if one did not know about energy conservation. This follows from time reversal balance applied to a reaction which may be written as products of probabilities i.e. $f(e_i)$. For a more general problem, the probability for e_i to interact is not proportional to $f(e_i)$ as in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In such a gas, one may consider a more complicated function $g(f(e_i))$ which gives the probability for e_i to react. Then ((1)) is replaced by:

$$g(e_1)g(e_2)=g(e_3)g(e_4) \text{ Taking } \ln \text{ and using } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \text{ yields } g(f) = \exp(-(e-u)/T). \quad ((2))$$

u, T are constant. Again $\ln(g(f))$ is a conserved quantity.

((1)) and ((2)) may also be obtained by using Shannon's entropy density. For ((1)), one defines

$-f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ and varies it with respect to $f(e_i)$ subject to the constraint $\sum e_i f(e_i)$. For ((2)) one may replace $f(e_i)$ with $g(f(e_i))$ (although one may also calculate a Kaniadakis entropy (1) which is different.)

Information Theory

Information theory seems to differ from statistical mechanics. For example, one may consider a long message written in English and define P_i as the probability for letter i in the alphabet to appear, e.g. P_1 is the probability to find the letter "a" in the initial message. The message is then transmitted to a reception point. At this destination, one expects P_i to be the same. If it is not, then the transmission process is very flawed. It is possible, however, that some signals representing letters "interact" with "something" along the way and convert into different letters at the reception point.

It seems Shannon dealt with such an example. In (2), Shannon's approach of finding a quantity called "information" is described. First, a function, called information i , is defined such that:

$i(p) > 0$ and decreases for decreasing probability p .

$$\text{For two independent probabilities } p \text{ and } q \quad i(p \cdot q) = i(p) + i(q) \quad ((3))$$

It is then found that i must be the \ln (logarithm) function.

In this note, we argue that $\ln(P_i)$ is a conserved quantity in the system which exists because P_i is the same for the original message and for the received one.

Information and Conservation of a Quantity

Consider an original long message in English with P_i being the probability for each letter to appear. The message is sent via signals for each letter to a receiver. On the way, each signal may “interact” with “something” and change from one letter into another. Thus, the received message may not be the same as the original, but P_i must be the same. If it is not, then the transmission process is guaranteed to change the message. Thus, we argue there is “conservation” of a quantity in this process because P_i is constrained to remain the same through the transmission.

Therefore, the scenario of a message being sent letter by letter is very similar to the passage of a particle in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in time. At time 0, there is a certain probability to have particles of energy e_i , namely $f(e_i)$. One may take a particle initially with e_1 . It will scatter into e_2 then e_3 etc. Finally, it will arrive at time t_2 as e_f , but $f(e_i)$ remains the same at $t=0$ and t_2 .

The problem for information theory becomes to find the conserved quantity. Imagine the conserved quantity is $Q(P_i)$. Then, if the signal for letter “a” interacts with “something” and the letter changes to “z”, one may write:

$$Q(P_1) = Q(P_26) + b \quad ((4))$$

where b is “like a photon in a reaction in which an electron drops from one energy level to another. If one considers the time reversed reaction to ((4)), one may argue that P_26 interacts with b to form P_1 i.e. letter “a”. If this interaction is independent, one may argue that:

$$P_26 * P(b) = P_1 \quad \text{or more generally : } P_j * P(b_{ji}) = P_i \quad ((5))$$

Taking \ln of ((5)) yields the conservation law which ensures that P_i remains unchanged over time. In other words $\ln(P_i)$, the information, is the conserved quantity in the problem.

$$\ln(P_i) - \ln(P_j) = b_{ji} \quad ((5b))$$

Here $\ln(P_i)$ is part of the initial message and P_j of the received message. The functions P_i and P_j are the same, so the sum of each is the same and $\sum b_{ji} = 0 \quad ((6))$

Thus, the b_i 's are like a photon bath.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue Shannon's information $\ln(P_i)$ is the conserved quantity in a problem for which a long message in English is transmitted. P_i is the probability for letter i to exist in the original message and it is also the probability for it to exist in the received message. The problem is that some signals representing particular initial letters may interact with “something”

and change into signals for different letters. Given the constraint that P_i must be the same in the original and final messages, we argue there should be a “conserved” quantity in this problem. We try to show it is $\ln(P_i)$. We also argue this is similar to statistical mechanics in which one has $f(e_i)$ at $t=0$ (the probability for a particle to have energy e_i) and the same $f(e_i)$ distribution at $t=t_2$. A particular particle with original energy e_1 may undergo many interactions and arrive at t_2 as e_f , but overall $f(e_i)$ does not change. This implies a conserved quantity, namely $\ln(f(e_i))$ which happens to be equal to energy in statistical mechanics. Even if one does not use the conservation of energy equation for a reaction, $\ln(f(e_i))$ follows as a conserved quantity from the writing of two body Maxwell-Boltzmann scattering interaction as $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_3)$ and taking \ln of both sides. For a more general reaction, $f(e_i)$ is replaced by $g(f(e_i))$, for example $g(f(e_i))=f/(1-f)$ for a Fermi-Dirac gas and $g(f)=f/(1+f)$ for a Bose-Einstein one.

The transmission of signals representing a message seems to follow the same physics of interactions, also with a conserved quantity and identical initial and final distributions.

References

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